

SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

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Research report on *COOPERATIVE ORGANISATIONAL MODELS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY in SWITZERLAND*

About SONNET: SONNET is a research project that aims to develop an understanding of diversity, processes, contributions and future potential of social innovation in the energy sector. It is co-funded by the European Commission and runs for three years, from 2019-2022. The SONNET consortium consists of 12 partners across Europe, including academics and city administrations. For more information, please visit our website: <https://sonnet-energy.eu>

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1 FOREWORD

SONNET (Social Innovation in Energy Transitions) brings diverse groups together to make sense of how social innovation can bring about a more sustainable energy sector in Europe. The project aims to co-create a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, successes and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector (SIE). We define SIE as a combination of ideas, objects and/or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy. As part of this work, we make use of an embedded case study approach to build a better understanding of the development of diverse SIE-fields (e.g. participatory incubation and experimentation, framings against specific energy pathways, local electricity exchange) over time. Our research questions that frame the case study work are:

- How do SIEs and SIE-fields emerge, develop and institutionalise over time?
- How do SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the ‘outside’ institutional environment and thereby co-shape the SIE-field over time?
- What are the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work and change the ‘outside’ institutional environment?

A SIE-field is an arena/space that includes a specific SIE as well as SIE-field-actors working on it and other field-actors enabling and/or impeding it. In this arena/ space these actors take one another and their actions into account and have a shared (but not necessarily consensual) understanding of a SIE and of their relationship to other actors. They recognise (but not necessarily follow) shared norms, beliefs and rules. SIE-fields are often not homogenous but are composed of actors with diverse and contradictory aims and interests. An example: The UK cooperative energy field includes SIE-initiatives and SIE-field-actors (e.g. Brighton Energy Co-op, Cooperative UK, Community Energy England, UK Government, City of Brighton), who have a shared understanding of an SIE, which exists as ‘organising under cooperative principles to generate renewable energy’.

The structure of this report is as follows. Section 2 provides a summary of the SIE-field relevant for this report and lists some key insights. Section 3 outlines the boundaries of the SIE-field and shows how it has been studied in the country context. Section 4 shows a visual development of the SIE-field. Section 5 tells the historical development of the SIE-field over time, including analytical/ interpretive reflections from the SONNET researchers and quotes from the actors involved in the field developments. Section 6 outlines key research findings, providing answers to the three research questions. Section 7 outlines recommendations for policymakers based on the findings. Finally, Section 9 outlines the methodological approach and includes a more detailed timeline of the SIE-field and its actors.

2 COOPERATIVE ORGANISATIONAL MODELS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY IN SWITZERLAND

In SONNET, we investigate the development of the SIE-field and its initiatives called renewable energy cooperatives (REC). With RECs we refer to organisational models through which citizens jointly own means of and participate in renewable energy production. Primarily, RECs aim to finance and operate renewable energy power plants but can also have other goals such as to sensitize local actors to the potential of local renewable energy and energy savings.

To determine what constitutes a cooperative organisational model, we rely on the cooperative principles provided by the European federation of renewable energy cooperatives (REScoop) and by the International Co-operative Alliance (ICA) respectively. These principles include i) concern for community, ii) voluntary and open membership, iii) democratic governance of the undertaking, and iv) autonomy and independence. At the organisational level, the cooperative principles can be implemented through a legal cooperative statute. However, what principles are represented in a cooperative statute varies from one country to another. Also, organisations with other statutes can adopt the cooperative principles without having a cooperative status. To explore the boundaries of the REC field in each of the investigated countries, we started with organisations adhering to the cooperative principles and identified empirically in which arena the majority of them are embedded.

In Switzerland, cooperative organisational models which correspond to these characteristics can be delimited among others by means of the legal form. In particular, cooperatives (*Genossenschaften*) have long been codified as a legal form for person-based corporations, thereby ensuring voluntary and open membership and democratic governance under Swiss law (OR Art. 828-926). In addition to this predestined form, other legal forms such as clubs, limited liability companies or, in some cases, joint-stock companies may also comply with the above criteria. Nevertheless, most of the identified organisations in Switzerland comply with the legal form of a cooperative. These energy cooperatives provide the organisational form for citizens to jointly finance, build and run photovoltaic facilities sometimes small hydroelectric power plants (other renewable energy technologies are only scarcely used). They thus imply a shift in the role of citizens vis-à-vis the incumbent energy system from passive consumers and voters to active prosumers which are engaged in investment decision-making at the level of individual facility projects. The development of this SIE-field has been strongly driven by changes in federal energy policy. But only recently, energy cooperatives have begun to organise beyond their local environments and find a common voice.

Key insights

For the SONNET project, the field of cooperative organisational models for renewable energy in Switzerland is particularly interesting because it reveals several important issues for social innovation in energy transitions. In particular, it illustrates that:

- The characterisation of energy cooperatives as socially innovative depends on their activities and ambitions rather than only on their statute as cooperative itself (at least for the Swiss case). With their idea about the role of citizens as active prosumers in the energy system being more and more institutionalised and even adopted by established actors, the social innovation of energy cooperatives is beginning to blur and could become more of a side effect rather than a priority intention.
- As the energy system is highly regulated, the design of energy policy is crucial for the development of SIE, as is embodied by energy cooperatives. In this respect, federal structures appear to be beneficial for such kind of social innovation as they allow for targeted support on the ground. However, it may be that because of this, socially innovative initiatives also remain entrenched in local structures and have difficulty organising themselves on a broader, national level.

3 INTRODUCTION TO COOPERATIVE ORGANISATIONAL MODELS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY IN SWITZERLAND

Since centuries, local self-help in the form of cooperative models has emerged in Switzerland whenever there was economic hardship or poor or inadequate quality of service. Also, in the energy system cooperatives are per se not a new phenomenon in Switzerland. They were already involved in the rural electrification between 1895 and 1925. Often under the name *Elektra*, these cooperatives set up distribution grids, built their own small hydropower plants or purchased electricity from larger producers, and supplied the local population with electricity (Gugerli, 1996). The main aim of these *old* energy cooperatives has usually been to supply the population with electricity at low-cost (Rivas et al., 2018). Despite many liquidations or transformations into other legal forms (around 50 since 1998), around 100 of these *old* energy cooperatives are still active today as distribution grid operators. Hence, they make up a substantial part of the around 650 electricity providers constituting the incumbent Swiss electricity system (Rivas et al. 2018; Interviewee 9). Shaped by the anti-nuclear power movement and later by the climate change discourse, a field consisting of around 200 *new* energy cooperatives has started to emerge since 1985 and accelerating after 2005. With their main aim to develop renewable energies that remain in the hands of citizens, they differ considerably from the older grid-operating cooperatives and are the focal point of this report. We thus cover the time period from 1985 to 2020 but especially focus on the development of energy cooperatives since 2005.

The main activity of these *new* energy cooperatives is to finance and operate renewable energy facilities (RE). For this, they mainly rely on photovoltaic installations (PV) on larger roofs whereas other technologies such as wind power are almost never used (Rivas et al. 2018). A small minority is active in heat generation from renewable sources and the operation of heating grids. Apart from the legal form and the use of renewable energy sources, however, there have been minimal linkages between the *photovoltaic cooperatives* and *heat*

cooperatives so far as they are subject to different regulation and organized through different intermediary organizations. Hence, the latter need to be considered as a separate field and will not be examined in more detail in this report. In recent years, the installation of PV facilities itself as well as new ways of selling the generated electricity have emerged as new business models in this field. However, there is currently no indication of further sectoral coupling or diversification of the business models beyond the PV technology among the large majority of cooperatives in the field (with some exceptions: see box on ADEV cooperative below, p. 10).

Distinguishing between the local or regional level and the national level is helpful to better understand the constellation of actors in the field of energy cooperatives. Most energy cooperatives have a local (or at most regional) focus, with municipalities and local energy suppliers standing out as key actors (Schmid et al., 2020). For a long time, the newly founded energy cooperatives were highly fragmented. Therefore, it has long been difficult to discern a nationally coherent field, in the sense that the actors mutually acknowledge each other and display some sort of interaction. It has only been in the last couple of years (since 2015) that intermediary actors have started to emerge to drive forward the institutionalisation of the field beyond the local level. Until today, no unitary and nationally operating intermediary actor has emerged that exclusively represents and organises the energy cooperatives, which distinguished the Swiss case from other countries (cf. Vernay and Sebi, 2020). Rather, numerous intermediary organisations have formed that represent different scopes or aspects of energy cooperatives, with some focusing only on a certain region, others focusing on the cooperative form (but not the energy aspect), and others focusing on solar energy (but not the cooperative aspect). At regional level, this includes the “Albert-Koechlin Foundation” in Central Switzerland or the “Chambre de l’économie sociale et solidaire” in Western Switzerland, which both seek to promote the establishment and development of energy cooperatives in their own region. At national level, it is the “Association of Independent Energy Producers” (VESE) that approximates most closely the function of an intermediary for energy cooperatives. However, its focus is not explicitly on the cooperative organisation per se but rather on the energy cooperatives’ role as independent power producers without an own grid. When it comes to the organisational form as cooperatives, the associations “idée cooperative” and “Cooperative Suisse” (now “Social Entrepreneurship Switzerland” SENS) are significant intermediaries in the field. And when it comes to the energy aspect, several associations, such as the “Swiss Solar Energy Industry Association Swissolar”, the “Swiss Solar Energy Association” SSES, or the “Swiss Energy Foundation” SES, focus on PV technology or renewable energy in general but not necessarily on the form of organisation i.e., the cooperative aspect. Our analysis shows that so far, the intermediary organisations that primarily deal with the energy aspect occupy a more central role in the field of energy cooperatives than those that primarily deal with the cooperative aspect, which may be regarded as rather peripheral. This suggests that the field is more likely to be constituted by contestations around energy issues, while there is less direct contestation in the field of the organisational form itself. However, this distinction between the energy aspect and the organisational aspect has started to blur most recently when it comes to intermediary representation. Firstly, with the “*Association for citizen energy Switzerland*” ASEC an organisation has emerged in 2018 which emphasizes the aspect of *citizen’s energy*. Yet, it has so far been active mainly in

the French-speaking part of Switzerland. Secondly, with the *Optima Solar Cooperative Switzerland* individual cooperatives have started to organise themselves in cooperative federations.

Other key actors in the field are the ADEV cooperative, the oldest of the new energy cooperatives and now a professionalised company, the “Swiss Energy Cooperative” (*Energiegenossenschaft Schweiz*) and the “Energy Transition Cooperative” (*Energiewendegenossenschaft*). The ADEV and Optima Solar Switzerland are the SIE initiatives examined in this report as they represent exceptional actors that have significantly shaped the development of the field through their activities (pioneers, formation of cooperative federations).

By financing, constructing, and operating PV facilities, the energy cooperatives in this field are mainly pursuing goals related to the energy transition, above all the phasing out of nuclear energy and the reduction of CO₂ emissions (Rivas et al. 2018). This is against the background of electricity production in the Swiss system that continues to substantially rely on nuclear energy (35.2 % of total electricity production). And while the share of CO₂ intensive energy sources is low—with a majority of electricity being produced by hydro power (56.4 %)—the share of new renewables such as wind and solar power remains small (4.2 %) (SFOE 2020). Hence, the discourse around renewable energy in general and energy cooperatives in particular had long been framed in relation to nuclear phase-out rather than climate change. With these goals the *new* energy cooperatives do not directly reflect the conventional goals of cooperatives, namely the advancement and safeguarding of certain economic interests of the cooperative members in joint self-help (as legally defined in Switzerland, OR Art. 828). Currently, these energy cooperatives do not address direct individual economic needs. The goals and narratives in the field are thus to be interpreted more as being oriented towards ideational goals and the common good (see Bauwens et al. 2019). More specifically, energy cooperatives were formed with the goal to increase the representation of citizens (or at least cooperative members) in decision-making on energy-related issues. This is to be understood against the background of the anti-nuclear movement of the 1970s and 1980s where the perception arose that relevant decisions—namely investment decisions—were beyond the control of the citizens (Interviewee 7) although energy supply in Switzerland continues to be largely owned by the public sector (and is thus often at least indirectly subject to certain democratic institutions).

"Nobody actually needs a solar plant today. The electricity comes from a European power system and costs almost nothing" (Interviewee 7)

"Our strategic goal is to increase the proportion of PV electricity in the grid" (Interviewee 4)

Key for investigating social innovation is identifying the perceived problem.

(Interviewee 4). Strong growth in the number of newly founded energy cooperatives after 2008 was mainly owed to favourable business conditions facilitated by a federal support instrument for renewable energies. After 2012, these conditions worsened due to a limitation in the aforementioned subsidies, resulting first in a decrease yet subsequent stabilisation of the number of new foundations of energy cooperatives. Since then, the development of existing energy cooperatives has been heavily dependent on finding suitable sales models for the generated electricity.

4 TIMELINE OF COOPERATIVE ORGANISATIONAL MODELS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY IN SWITZERLAND

Figure 1 shows the innovation timeline of the field of cooperative organisational models for renewable energy in Switzerland. The figure is divided into four levels. The top level shows relevant developments in Swiss federal energy policy for the field. Below this, follow developments with regard to intermediary organisations within the field that are operating on a Switzerland-wide basis. The third level focuses on regional/local phenomena, i.e. the formation of individual key cooperatives or regionally active intermediaries. Finally, the fourth, lowest level illustrates how many new energy cooperatives were founded per year (as well as the waiting list for the federal funding instrument, KEV, see below for more details, p. 15).

Figure 1: Innovation timeline of cooperative organisational models for renewable energy in Switzerland

5 EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF COOPERATIVE ORGANISATIONAL MODELS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY IN SWITZERLAND OVER TIME

PHASE 1: First wave of new foundations: Anti-nuclear protest and pioneering renewables (1985-2000)

The starting point for the field of new renewable energy cooperatives in Switzerland was the long-lasting struggle over nuclear power starting in the 1960s, and especially the ultimately successful protests movement against the planned nuclear power plant in Kaiseraugst in the 1970s and 1980s as well as the Chernobyl nuclear accident in 1986. The first new energy cooperative founded in these years was ADEV in 1985 (see box below). It was also during these decades that interest groups were formed which today are still important intermediary organisations for renewable energies and thus indirectly for energy cooperatives, including the “Swiss Solar Energy Association” SSES (*Schweizer Verband für Solarenergie*) in 1974 and the “Swiss Energy Foundation” SES (*Schweizer Energie Stiftung*) in 1976.

Introduction ADEV cooperative

In 1985, the first new energy cooperative was established in the form of the ‘Working Group for Decentralised Energy Supply’ ADEV (*Arbeitsgruppe Dezentrale Energieversorgung*). Its aim was not only to expand renewable energies but to achieve this with public participation. Initially without paid employees for several years, it was intended to ensure that renewable energies were firmly anchored in society and that it was not simply a matter of making money (Interviewee 8).

To this day, ADEV has realised a large number of lighthouse projects for the Swiss energy system. Decentralised energy production from renewable energies and efficient local consumption continue to be among the main concerns. However, unlike the vast majority of other energy cooperatives, ADEV is not only active in the PV sector but also constructs and operates small hydroelectric power plants, wind turbines, central heating plants and local heating networks and operates such infrastructure for third parties.

In terms of its organisational structure, ADEV has undergone significant developments since its foundation and differs considerably from other energy cooperatives. It has founded several subsidiaries focusing on the various energy sectors (ADEV Wasserkraftwerk AG, ADEV Solarstrom AG, ADEV Windkraft AG and ADEV Ökowärme AG).

At the beginning of this first wave of newly formed energy cooperatives, their focus was not yet on solar energy as this was far too expensive at the time. Rather, the main thrust—also by the ADEV—was to bring small, already decommissioned hydroelectric power plants back into operation. In the course of the 1990s, however, when around 40 new energy cooperatives were founded, solar energy became increasingly important. Also, a few energy cooperatives emerged which built their own heating grids and supplied them with heat from wood chip firing (less than 20 to date). Nevertheless, electricity generation through PV increasingly became the core activity of Swiss energy cooperatives (Rivas et al. 2018). A first breakthrough for the establishment of energy cooperatives was the introduction of the *16-Räppler* regulation in 1991 (as part of the federal government’s “Decision on the use of energy”, *Energienutzungsbeschluss*) since it established a statutory minimum remuneration per kilowatt hour fed into the grid and thus provided an important basis for the development of new, independent producers without their own distribution grid (ADEV Anniversary Brochure 1985-2010). Although still at a miniscule level, this regulation provided a minimal reliable income stream and thus certain investment securities to the cooperatives. This issue of how to sell generated electricity continues to be a major struggle for Swiss energy cooperatives to date, as further explained below (see Phase 4 in this chapter, p. 17ff).

Cooperative activity in the electricity sector is as old as the sector itself.

During this early phase, further significant developments for the emerging field of energy cooperatives happened in the realm of energy policy. In accordance with the principle of subsidiarity in Switzerland’s federal system, energy supply has originally been the primary responsibility of municipalities, the lowest administrative level of government. Even though the federal government had been programmatically engaged since the 1960s, its formal responsibilities in energy policy was confined to the regulation of the nuclear sector and supervisory functions related to hydropower and safety aspects of low and high-voltage installations (Sager, 2014). Similarly, it was not until 1979 that the first comprehensive energy act was adopted at the cantonal level, the subnational entities constituting the Swiss confederation (Strebel, 2011).

It was not until the 1973 oil crisis, the emerging climate and sustainability debates (e.g., Brundtland Report 1987), and the Chernobyl reactor accident that the energy sector became increasingly governed and regulated at the federal level. After two earlier failed attempts, an amendment to the Swiss constitution on energy was only included in 1990 following a mandatory referendum (Zünd, 2020), which empowered the federal government to define principles for the expansion and consumption of energy (Sager, 2014; Rieder and Strotz, 2018). Generally, the consolidation of energy policy at the federal level in this first phase provided the foundation for a more active subsidisation of renewable energies that followed. Ultimately, this also promoted the founding and development of energy cooperatives by facilitating more secure and economical business models.

Regulative, normative and/ or cultural cognitive institutions

In SONNET, we differentiate between regulative, normative, and cultural cognitive institutions that might shape the development of a SIE field. Regulative institutions encompass laws, rules, standards, and policies; normative institutions are norms and value systems; and cultural cognitive institutions include conceptions of reality, binding expectations as well as common beliefs.

In the Swiss case, the adoption of the cooperative model to promote renewable energies is no coincidence. Switzerland has a long tradition of organizing economic activities in the form of cooperatives especially in the agricultural sector. Cooperative-like entities and their subsequent regulations date back to the Early Middle Ages and are even considered to be connected to the formation of Swiss municipalities (Arnold, 2005; Purtschert, 2005; See also Blümle, 1969).

“Historically, cooperatives have emerged in Switzerland whenever there has been economic hardship, poor quality or lack of service, for instance when there was insufficient food 150 years ago, when small farmers could not receive loans 100 years ago, or when the housing market has overheated in recent decades” (Interviewee 5).

That also means that the cooperative model is well embedded in Swiss society with various implications on institutional norms, value systems and the legitimacy of roles and economic activities in different sectors such as housing, agriculture, retail trade and banking. As a result, around 9 000-10 000 cooperatives are active today (Aeschbacher and Liechtsteiner, 2014), jointly accounting for 17-18 % of the Swiss GDP (Interviewee 5). The reliance on the cooperative model can therefore be understood as a cultural, normative institution in that cooperatives are used to address societal problems by citizens acting on their own initiative. Further deliberations, especially on regulative institutions, can be found in the box below on the ‘outside’ institutional environment.

PHASE 2: Intermezzo and developments in Swiss energy policy (1998-2005)

After the first wave of foundations of about 40 energy cooperatives between 1985 and 1997, there were hardly any new foundations between 1998 and 2005. Nor did any new intermediary actors emerge at this time to ensure the networking of these newly founded energy cooperatives. Many of these cooperatives did not develop much further, and only a few achieved to make steps towards professionalisation such as paid employment and to

construct multiple facilities (Rivas et al. 2018). One exception is ADEV which developed to a professionalised company and to date has built and operates over 115 production plants, both in electricity and heat generation (see box on ADEV, p.10).

Yet, further pivotal decisions in energy policy took place during these years. In 1998, the first Swiss energy act came into force based on the constitutionalisation of energy policy in 1990 described above. Furthermore, following the efforts of the European Union and its member states to open their electricity markets in the 1990s, the Swiss government also pursued the goal of liberalising the Swiss electricity system and linking it to the European market (Sager, 2014). However, the Electricity Market Act, intended to achieve this objective, was rejected in a referendum in 2002. Only later, in 2007, a new act foresaw a gradual opening and provided that since 2009 large consumers (annual consumption of more than 100 MWh) could choose their electricity supplier. Small consumers, on the other hand, remain in the territorial monopolies of individual energy suppliers and thus cannot switch to another supplier of their choice. The complete opening of the market, including for small consumers, has been repeatedly postponed, but is now planned again for the coming years (in April 2020 the Federal Council decided in favour of adapting a new law by 2021). This situation has had a substantial effect on possible business models for energy cooperatives in Switzerland, as explained in detail below (Phase 4, p.20ff.).

‘Outside’ institutional environment shaping the development of the SIE-field

In SONNET, we consider a SIE-field to be nested in a larger encompassing institutional environment, consisting of both formal and informal institutions. We are interested to understand how dominant institutions (regulative, normative, and cultural cognitive elements) within this ‘outside’ institutional environment influence the emergence and development of SIE within a SIE-field.

In the Swiss case, the multi-level governance character of the Swiss energy policy and system has major implications for the energy cooperatives as part of the ‘outside’ institutional environment. Switzerland’s energy policy and energy system features a multi-level governance structure. The constitutionalisation of energy policy as task of the federal government after 1990 has not been tantamount to a complete shift of energy policy to the federal level as the cantons and municipalities retain substantial powers and responsibilities (Sager, 2014). It is against this background that municipalities are key local actors for energy cooperatives. In about half of the energy cooperatives, a municipality is a member itself. Often it is municipal politicians who helped to establish the cooperatives, and one third of the energy cooperatives were even initiated by municipalities or actors from the municipality (Rivas et al. 2018). And due to their autonomy and leeway for own energy policy in the Swiss federal system, municipalities can financially

support energy cooperatives (Meister et al. 2020). In individual cases, municipal policies were even created to bridge the uncertainty which had long surrounded the Swiss feed-in tariff scheme KEV, thus directly supporting energy cooperatives (Schmid et al. 2020).

The historically decentralised energy governance also continues to be reflected in the structure of the energy system. As already mentioned, in 2017 around 650 electricity providers were active, despite ongoing consolidation. Among these utilities, however, there are major differences. Many of them supply only a single municipality with electricity, more than half of them have 10 or fewer employees (Interviewee 9) and around 70% have no generation capacity of their own. On the other hand, others, such as Alpiq, BKW, Axpo, CKW, ewz, or Repower, are large companies which supply regional and sometimes supra-cantonal areas and own and operate most of Switzerland's electricity generation capacity (Verhoog and Finger, 2016). And although the energy utilities are largely owned by the cantons and municipalities (around 89% of the capital stock, SFOE, 2018), there are again major differences in the public corporate governance of these organisations, with some acting as part of the municipal administration to others being independent public or private companies with majority public sector holdings (Mühlemeier, 2018).

These features of the Swiss energy system have significant implications for energy cooperatives. Certainly, the decentralised and small-scale character of energy system has the potential advantage that energy cooperatives may easier gain access to energy suppliers as they operate on similar spatial scales. However, the relationships between energy cooperatives and (local) energy suppliers are diverse and sometimes conflictual. Usually, such conflicts are about various specific aspects of the framework conditions that the energy suppliers provide for new actors such as energy cooperatives (e.g. metering costs, purchase price for electricity fed into the grid, provision of contact persons).

It is not fully clear which conditions shape these relationships as no clear pattern emerges between capacities, governance, ownership structure of individual energy suppliers on one side and the nature of their relationship to the cooperative on the other. A sole conceivable tendency is that it is mostly medium-sized energy supplier which struggle in dealing with emerging actors and new participation models in the energy sector. The smaller ones are very customer-oriented and flexible, and the large ones have sufficient capacity to adapt quickly to new situations. The medium-sized ones, on the other hand, seem to have a tendency towards more rigid processes (Interviewee 9). However, this thesis requires further research.

In combination, these features of the 'outside' institutional environment resulted in the fact that the field of energy cooperative has long been strongly fragmented in the sense that the individual

cooperatives had predominantly a local focus while not collaborating, networking, or even communicating at a superordinate, especially national level. This is due to the fact that, apart from certain nationally determined framework conditions, decisive conditions for the business environment of energy cooperatives such as municipal support or the relationship to the energy suppliers are set at the local level.

PHASE 3: Second wave of new foundations and federal RE support schemes (2005-2012)

It was not until 2005 that the number of newly founded cooperatives started to increase again, resulting in a boom of new foundations. The conditions for energy cooperatives improved considerably, mainly due to newly introduced policy instruments for the promotion of renewable energies by the federal government. These instruments were first, the “Financing of additional cost” MKF scheme (*Mehrkostenfinanzierung*) introduced in 2005, and second, the “Feed-in remuneration at cost” KEV scheme (*Kostendeckende Einspeisevergütung*) introduced in 2009. They guaranteed RE facility operators fixed remuneration for electricity fed into the grid over a period of 20 years, based on the production costs of a reference plant. This made it possible for the energy cooperatives that benefited from these subsidies to cost-effectively operate PV plants over a long period of time, which greatly improved the investment security for projects as well as the economic viability of the cooperatives.

Subsequent to the introduction of these policy instruments, the number of newly founded cooperatives increased considerably every year between 2009 and 2012 (see Figure 1, p. 9) due to the security of investment granted by the KEV, but also due to the sharp drop in the production costs of photovoltaics following extensive subsidisation under the “German Renewable Energy Sources Act” (EEG) and the reactor accident in Fukushima.

Introduction Optima Solar Schweiz cooperative

The cooperative Optima Solar Solothurn was founded in 2011 and has since established more than 20 PV plants with a total capacity of more than 2'400 kWp. This achievement has in part been facilitated by cooperation with the energy supplier of the city of Solothurn, which buys considerable quantities of electricity from the energy cooperative each year and offers it to end consumers in the form of a special regional electricity product "So near, so good" (e-mail Optima Solar Switzerland).

In 2013, Optima Solar Switzerland was founded as a cooperative federation (an umbrella cooperative for individual cooperatives) with the idea to replicate the model and brand, to provide

administrative support, and to bundle the distribution of guarantees of origin. Furthermore, the federation started commenting on federal energy policy developments, not least in a letter to Federal Councilor Sommaruga, Head of the Federal Department of the Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications, with proposals for improving the framework conditions for decentralised electricity producers.

The Optima Solar cooperatives are among the most successful energy cooperatives founded since 2005 when it comes to the deployment of new PV installations, and are shaping the field by introducing the idea of a cooperative federation. This is unique in that it is a bottom-up development that seeks to bundle operational tasks while the other recently established associations (such as VESE, ASEC) focus more on consultation and advocacy.

This phase also included the foundations of the “Optima Solar Solothurn” cooperative (2011), which subsequently set up “Optima Solar Schweiz”, and of the “Energy Cooperative Switzerland” (*Energiegenossenschaft Schweiz*) (2012). One characteristic of this second wave of new energy cooperatives is that anti-nuclear motives no longer dominate as primary goals but rather the climate issues and the energy transition in general as expressed in the following quote:

“We do not want an against, we want a pro. We no longer want to merely shut down the nuclear power plants, we want a pro for the whole energy transition” (Interviewee 7)

SIE changing social relations

In SONNET we think of social innovation in the energy sector (SIE) as combination of ideas, objects and/or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy.

When it comes to Swiss energy cooperatives, it is not their legal form per se that constitutes them as social innovation since cooperatives in the energy sector are not necessarily a novel phenomenon. Rather, the link to social innovation is multifaceted, relating to their goals and ambitions as well as the activities how those are implemented. Most importantly, this concerns the possibility for citizens to directly participate in decision-making and ownership of renewable energy facilities. The major change of social relations that energy cooperatives bring about

concerns the relationship between individual citizens and the energy system. Previously, the role of citizens with respect to energy supply was mainly limited to that of consumers. Beyond this, they could only indirectly influence strategic decisions in the energy system in their capacity as constituents, be it by voting for representatives or by voting in referenda at different levels of government. Through their participation in energy cooperatives, this role and consequentially the relationship to the energy system changes. From an economic point of view, citizens are moving from consumers to producers. From a political point of view, they become active co-creators of the energy system who influence not only strategic but also more operational decisions.

It is intriguing that this aspect of social innovation of energy cooperatives carries a high significance in the Swiss system. After all, given the extensively developed direct-democratic institutions combined with the continuing prominent role of the state in the energy system (state ownership of energy suppliers, decentralisation), citizens have a relatively strong influence on developments in the energy system (e.g., through municipal referenda or assemblies on the energy strategy of the energy supplier if owned by the municipality). Nevertheless, the shift of citizen roles towards more active shapers of the energy transition, as facilitated in energy cooperatives, seems to remain central.

Another facet of social innovation may concern how the cooperative idea is implemented. Cooperatives traditionally focus on promoting the common individual economic interests of the cooperative members. In the case of (Swiss) energy cooperatives, on the other hand, the format is used to promote the members' ideational goals, thus expanding the purpose of the cooperative idea (Interviewee 1). Finally, the pioneering activities of energy cooperatives may mark a social innovation in their effect as they have helped to establish the legitimacy of photovoltaics as a credible and viable new energy technology.

"Our cooperative has built fewer and fewer plants since 2013 (none at all in 2019) as it is becoming increasingly difficult"
(Interviewee 4)

PHASE 4: Aggravating conditions: Weakening of federal support for renewable energies, uncertainty and decline of number of new foundations (2012-2014)

After the boom phase between 2005 and 2011, the field of energy cooperatives experienced a setback and more difficult conditions after 2012 due to federal support policy for renewables. Sales of the generated electricity increasingly became the key challenge.

After 2012, the number of newly founded energy cooperatives sharply dropped due to changing support conditions. The KEV scheme was financed by a politically determined grid surcharge per consumed kWh (initially CHF 0.006 / kWh, today CHF 0.023 / kWh). Consequently, the available financial resources were limited from the outset and due to a high number of projects applying for KEV financing, a long waiting list soon developed (see Figure 1, p. 9). Although the grid surcharge was repeatedly increased, almost 40 000 projects (or 2 000 MW of projected capacity respectively) (Verhoog and Finger, 2016) had accumulated on this waiting list by 2015. However, by 2012 it was already unlikely for new projects to ever receive KEV funding, leaving the energy cooperatives with high uncertainty about the long-term economic viability of their business models. 2012 therefore constitutes a critical turning point in the field's recent development. Nevertheless, the number of new cooperatives did not fall to zero, though significantly fewer new energy cooperatives were founded each year after 2012.

"The biggest challenge is to find a roof for a PV system that is large enough to make it worthwhile for an energy cooperative to install it and where the electricity generated can be sold in a reasonable way" (Interviewee 7).

Further developments took place at the level of federal energy policy. In 2014, a new instrument was introduced to reduce the waiting list for KEV subsidy: The one-off investment grants which provide a single investment contribution of up to 30% for small plants (<30 kW) as an alternative to KEV support. Furthermore, the right to self-consumption of self-generated electricity was explicitly granted. Another major development of these years was the adoption of the Energy Strategy 2050 as federal energy strategy, which stipulates the phasing out of nuclear power and expansion of electricity generation from hydropower to 37 400 GWh and from other renewables to 11 400 GWh by 2035, partially as response to the Fukushima reactor accident (for reference: net electricity production in 2019 was around 67 800 GWh, SFOE, 2020).

Policies and policy making

Specific policies and their formation are relevant to SIE fields. This section analyses such policies in terms of their relevance to the field, the governance levels involved, how SIE actors and their interests are taken into account in the policy-making processes, and the extent to which the resulting policies empower SIE actors.

Although important conditions for the development of the field of energy cooperatives are to be attributed to the local area, it is also strongly affected by changes in energy policy at the federal level. The introduction of the "Feed-in remuneration at cost" scheme (KEV) in 2009 created high investment security for new renewable energy facilities and thus made it possible for the energy cooperatives to plan long-term. This policy instrument has been key to the many new foundations

of energy cooperatives by creating a protected niche for the foundation process and the build-up of organisational and knowledge resources. Subsequently, it was also the de-facto removal of the option to receive KEV support after 2012 which led to a decline in the number of new foundations.

This may be understood as a shift of the enabling conditions for energy cooperatives from the federal to the local level when it comes to policy support. When KEV support was no longer an option, it was primarily support from municipalities or municipally owned energy suppliers which provided the conditions for the successful development of individual cooperatives. In some cases, support instruments for renewable energies were explicitly introduced as part of municipal energy policy in order to bridge the gap left by the KEV, for instance a municipal feed-in tariff scheme or investment contributions (Schmid et al. 2020). This can be understood as a case of multi-level reinforcement in which different levels of governance support complement each other (Schreurs and Tiberghien. 2007). Yet, the federal level remains central in determining the general conditions under which the energy cooperatives operate, especially by regulating the tariffs the energy suppliers are required to pay for electricity fed into the grid and by continuing efforts to promote photovoltaics through subsidies. Municipal policy can then have an enabling effect within these framework conditions, sometimes through compensating for shortcomings in energy policy of superior levels (Schmid et al. 2020).

Particularly in recent years, energy cooperatives have started to become increasingly engaged in policy making processes at the federal level. This has been primarily achieved through the establishment of the «Association of Independent Energy Producers» (VESE) which participates in consultation processes for new legislation, but also through individual cooperative voicing their opinions and suggestions in such processes.

For the existing energy cooperatives, these new conditions after KEV meant welcome support but also increased uncertainty for investment decisions. On the one hand, the one-off investment grants helped improve the economic viability of PV facilities as lower investment sums needed to be amortised. On the other hand, selling the generated electricity in a way that covered the remaining costs and possibly allowed for a small return on the cooperative capital remains a major challenge for energy cooperatives to date (Rivas et al. 2018). In this matter of electricity sales, the relevance of the regulation i.e., the not fully liberalised state of the Swiss electricity market, as described above (see box on 'outside' institutional environment, p. 13f.) becomes evident. This is because apart from the KEV scheme, the energy cooperatives have only two options: They can either sell the generated electricity to the distribution grid operator of the territorial monopoly who is obliged to purchase it at a regulated price or sell the generated electricity locally for self-consumption. In what follows, both sales channels will be explained in detail, as this has been the central issue affecting energy cooperatives in this phase and continuing until today.

Sales of generated electricity to distribution system operators

As first option the generated electricity may be fed into the grid and sold to the distribution grid operator (DSO). In this case, the minimum remuneration pursuant to the Swiss Federal Energy Ordinance is determined by the avoided costs of the grid operator for the procurement of equivalent energy (until 2017¹). These remunerations are generally redefined annually by the DSOs. Hence, the amount of the remuneration is tied to the development of the electricity market price or, in cases of remuneration above the minimal requirement, depends on the benevolence of the DSOs. For facilities like photovoltaic plants, which usually are in operation for more than 25 years, this creates significant uncertainties for investment decisions. And as data provided by the association VESE disclose, these remunerations vary considerably between the individual DSOs (see Figure 2, next page). Note that we refer to current numbers on this topic for the rest of this paragraph as it continues to be a major issue until today. While some distribution system operators currently pay up to CHF 0.13 / kWh, others pay much less (down to less than CHF 0.04 / kWh), which severely hampers the economically viable financing and operation of PV systems despite ongoing reduction of production costs. The regulatory bottom line, with a sole orientation on avoided costs or the market price respectively, is probably only at a remuneration of CHF 0.02 / kWh (Interviewee 7). Any higher remunerations are therefore either attributable to higher production costs of the energy provider or to the benevolence of DSOs, respectively policy guidelines issued by their owners e.g., municipalities or cantons. Against this background, the current remunerations of at least some distribution network operators allow cost-covering financing and operation of new PV systems (approx. CHF 0.08 / kWh,

¹ Since 2018 the minimum remuneration pursuant to the Swiss Federal Energy Ordinance has newly been determined by the costs of the grid operator for the procurement of equivalent electricity from third parties as well as the production costs of the own production facilities.

Interviewee 7). However, there is little certainty as to how these remunerations will develop over the coming decades, which means a high degree of investment uncertainty.

Remuneration for electricity fed into the grid (Rp. / kWh)

Figure 2: Feed-in tariffs of distribution grid providers in the year 2020 (for energy and certificate of origin of 50 kVA photovoltaics installation without self-consumption; “Rp.”: Swiss Centimes, 1 € = 108 Rp. (as of December 16, 2020). Source of graph: VESE (2020).

Power and power relations (power to + power over + power with)

Power is broadly understood as the relational and structural (in)capacity of actors to mobilise resources and institutions to achieve a goal. SIEs can refer to the resources being mobilised and/or the goals being aspired. In SONNET, we differentiate between different types of power:

- Power to: Actors having different kinds/levels of power/capacity to mobilize SIE-resources-related resources and/or to achieve SIE-related goals.
- Power over others: Actors having power over others in SIE-related processes including issues of inequality, exclusion, conflict, dependency, oppression & exploitation.
- Power with (collective power): Actors holding & exercising power together with other actors to achieve collective (SIE-related) goal, through e.g., strategic collaboration, pooling resources, joining forces, etc.

With respect to the examined case, a first issue of power concern the social innovation of energy cooperatives itself, namely the shift in the role of citizens towards active co-creators and investment decision-makers in the energy system, which can be understood as empowerment (power to). Although citizens already hold considerable power in the Swiss system due to extensive direct-democratic institutions, participation in a cooperative gives them the opportunity to participate in shaping their own energy environment on a level previously reserved for actors in the energy system and at best only indirectly under the control of citizens. However, it should be noted that only a small part of the population is active in energy cooperatives and therefore representativeness of public majority opinion cannot be necessarily claimed.

Another important aspect concerning power relations is the strong dependence of energy cooperatives on energy suppliers, resulting from electricity market regulation and the territorial monopolies in supply. Hence, the success of energy cooperatives strongly depends on the prices at which the generated electricity is purchased by the energy suppliers. This can be both an enabling or hindering relationship, depending on whether the remuneration renders a viable operation of PV facilities practically impossible or make it attractive to do so. This strong dependency represents a form of power over others. With the advent of self-consumption models, this dependency weakens as the cooperatives can negotiate conditions and conclude contracts directly with their customers. However, the dependency on energy suppliers persists.

Finally, a form of power with is represented in the networking of the energy cooperatives in the “Association of Independent Energy Producers” VESE (see below: phase 5, p. 25). This has given

them more power to influence policy-making processes, which they did not have before as very fragmented actors. The formation of intermediary actors also creates a means of tackling the dependencies on energy suppliers (as power over issue) described above. This is achieved, for instance, by VESE publicly presenting the differences in remunerations paid by the suppliers, negotiating with larger energy suppliers, or informing energy cooperatives about new rights and obligations under new energy regulations (e.g., who must pay for meter costs).

Occasionally, this challenge is met by entering into bilateral agreements with the distribution system operators on long-term remunerations or by more comprehensive collaboration models. One example for this is model of the association “Sunraising” in the city of Bern, through which 20 PV facilities have already been implemented in cooperation with the city-administration and the energy supplier of the city. As a result of the cooperation with the energy provider, it is feasible in this model that the generated electricity of these facilities has a direct bearing on their electricity bill from the energy provider even for investors who are not directly located at the site of the facilities (i.e., not through own consumption). Hence, in this model it is possible to directly benefit from the electricity production of the plant the association members invested in even without direct own consumption (Participatory observation 1).

Overall, however, such models are only possible if the energy provider is willing to cooperate in such a manner. This is also a factor in the question regarding the future liberalisation of the electricity market. After all, it is easier for energy suppliers to pay higher remuneration if they can pass on the higher costs to end customers in the monopoly. This leeway may become under pressure in a fully liberalised market with higher competition.

“If the remunerations for electricity fed into the grid are above the market price, they are passed on to the customers in the monopoly. Ultimately, it is accounted for via the production costs which means that the customers in the monopoly pay more. This becomes even more difficult with liberalisation” (Interviewee 9).

Apart from the electricity itself, the *guarantees of origin* (HKN) can also be sold. The HKNs indicate the quality of the electricity generated. In many remunerations for electricity fed into the grid discussed above (p. 22f.), the *green added value* attested via the HKN is already included in the price (see Figure 2, p. 21). Unlike the electricity itself, however, HKNs can be traded freely. Some energy cooperatives sell the HKNs to their members or third parties (Rivas et al. 2018). Also, there are various platforms for trading such HKNs. This trade can take place throughout Europe as the Swiss HKNs adhere to the European Energy Certificate System. This trade of HKN is important for energy suppliers for their ability to offer a green electricity mix to end consumers, even if the physical electricity is not, e.g., nuclear electricity. Due to this integration into the European market for certificates energy suppliers can obtain HKN at relatively low cost (approx. CHF 0.01-0.02 /kWh), one example being the purchase of certificates from Norwegian hydropower. This also puts pressure on the prices that energy

cooperatives can receive for their own HKNs, especially in cooperation models with energy supply. For this reason, there are calls in the field for a restriction of the Europe-wide trading of certificates or at least a more differentiated design of the HKNs (emphasis on regionality).

"That leaves the public buildings. These are our favourite roofs" (Interviewee 7)

Sales of generated electricity via self-consumption

The second alternative to selling the generated electricity is self-consumption, which has been explicitly recognised by law since 2014. Self-consumption describes the model in which the generated electricity is consumed directly on site without using the distribution grid. Nevertheless, a connection to the distribution grid is still provided in order to purchase additionally required electricity or to sell surplus electricity (here too, the distribution grid operator is obliged to purchase the surplus). It is not necessary that the owner of a plant, the one of the roof, and the consumer of the electricity are the same party. Since the costs for grid usage and levies (up to 65% of the usual electricity price, imposed via grid usage) are omitted in case of self-consumption, the price for electricity generated by photovoltaic systems can be correspondingly higher and thus facilitate economic business models. However, the long operating horizon of PV systems also poses challenges in terms of security of investment. This is because it must be possible to conclude long-term roof usage and power purchase agreements to plan viable business models. Often, these time horizons are far too long for many roof owners and potential buyers, for example for many private companies. This makes the public sector—especially municipalities—predestined partners for and customers of energy cooperatives. Municipalities usually have large roofs e.g., of school buildings, swimming pools or gymnasiums and are able to conclude long-term contracts.

Key changes over time

This box examines key changes that have critically influenced the emergence and development of the SIE-field or co-shaped the SIE-field and 'outside' institutional environment.

Out of the three most important key changes in the field of Swiss energy cooperatives in the last 15 years two have been marked by developments in federal energy policy. These were, firstly the introduction of the "Feed-in remuneration at cost" scheme (KEV) in 2008, which allowed for economically viable and long-term secure business model, and secondly the subsequent de-facto discontinuation of the option to receive this support for new installations in 2012. The introduction of the KEV scheme created protected spaces in which the newly founded energy cooperatives could establish themselves and develop the required knowledge and organisational capacities. The removal of these protected spaces for future installations then led to a new dynamic in the field in the sense as the newly founded cooperatives began to develop their business models (e.g., cooperative models with energy suppliers, self-consumption models) as well as new intermediary organisations and networks.

This increased cooperation can then be understood as a third key change in the field. In contrast to the former two, it emerged out of the field itself while still being contingent upon these previous policy changes, at least partially. It was only through increased cooperation and the emergence of intermediary actors that a more coherent national field emerge from 2015 onwards. The establishment of the “Association of Independent Energy Producers” VESE in this year, which can be seen as main association for energy cooperatives, thus stands for a third key change. As of now, it cannot be adequately assessed to what extent the facilitation of self-consumption communities after 2018/2019 will represent another turning point driven by a policy change.

PHASE 5: Kick-off of self-structuring of the field through emergence of intermediary organisations (2015-today)

While only a few new energy cooperatives were founded, the changes in the years between 2012 and 2014 led to developments among the existing cooperatives which resulted in strong acceleration of the self-structuring of the field from 2015 onwards, especially through the formation of intermediary organisations. The deterioration of conditions after 2012 showed the high impact of federal-level legislation on the business environment of energy cooperatives and thus revealed the increased need to bring their interests and concerns into the federal legislative process. At this point, however, the field of energy cooperatives was highly fragmented and rather characterised by many small local or at most regional “fields” without a national field of energy cooperatives emerging with mutual perception and communication beyond the regional level. Still in 2016, more than half of all cooperatives were not organised in any sort of association (Rivas et al. 2018). This has been accompanied by many cooperatives facing organisational challenges. In 2016, the activities of more than half of the energy cooperatives founded after 2005 were entirely based on voluntary work (Rivas et al. 2018). Especially with increasingly complicated business models such as self-consumption communities (see below, p. 30) energy cooperatives often reach their capacity limits. This point was addressed in the interview with a SIE-field actor (Interviewee 7):

“There is great enthusiasm and there are people willing to do a lot of volunteer work with an ideational goal, just like in an association. Nevertheless, it is necessary to professionalise. The question is about the critical size. There is a death-valley. [The cooperatives] are too big to do it part-time as volunteers but still too small to manage it professionally, with their own employees” (Interviewee 7).

Interestingly, in this respect they are no different from the energy cooperatives founded between 1990 and 2000 which additionally face a generation gap and have difficulties in finding successors in their management. It was

at least partially due to these limited capacities that the energy cooperatives were much less networked with each other before 2015. Many were primarily concerned with their local business environment. This often meant that there was a lack of exchange of experience and of more powerful interest representation at supra-local—especially federal—political level. As a response to these challenges, various organisations have emerged since 2015 which directly or indirectly provide intermediary functions to the energy cooperatives.

In 2015 the “Association of Independent Energy Producers” (VESE) was founded as a sub-group of the “Swiss Association for Solar Energy” (SSES). Today, it embodies the most important interest group for energy cooperatives in Switzerland when it comes to the intermediary energy cooperatives are a member of. However, VESE not only represents energy cooperatives but also other electricity producers without their own grid. It is therefore not explicitly cooperative-specific even though most of its members are cooperatives. VESE provides support in technical, administrative, and legal matters and promotes the exchange of experience among its members. Moreover, it advocates for better framework conditions of decentralised, independent energy production at the federal political level and vis-à-vis energy producers (Interviewee 7). In this respect, a key activity is the formulation of statements in the consultation procedures² on new energy legislation at the federal level. Finally, VESE organises bi-annual conferences which aim to transfer knowledge and exchange experience among its members. Nowadays, VESE represents the interests of more than 200 independent energy producers.

² “The consultation procedure is the stage during the pre-legislative process in which endeavours of the federal government of considerable political, financial, economic, ecological, social or cultural significance are scrutinized for their factual accuracy, feasibility and acceptance. To this end, the proposal is submitted to the cantons, the parties represented in the federal assembly, the umbrella organisations of the municipalities, cities and mountain regions, the umbrella organisations of the business community and other interested parties in individual cases” (Federal Council, 2020).

In 2016, the Albert Koechlin Foundation launched a program to promote energy cooperatives in Central Switzerland. The program aims to establish and develop as many locally based energy cooperatives as possible in Central Switzerland:

“It is important that more energy cooperatives are founded in Central Switzerland. The cooperatives form decentralised nuclei for the further development of the individual villages in the area of ‘renewable energy production and energy storage’” (Albert Koechlin Stiftung, 2019).

To this end, the program provides basic materials for the formal procedures needed when setting up cooperatives, provides financial support for the costs of foundation, and promotes the exchange between existing energy cooperatives through annual meetings. These activities helped the foundation of several new energy cooperatives in Central Switzerland. It was partially due to this programme that the downward trend in the number of new companies founded each year came to a halt in 2018 and that, for the first time since 2012, more energy cooperatives were founded than in the previous year.

Diversity, contestations and relations between actors

To better understand institutional change, we analyse SIE field contestations, i.e. debates among SIE-field-actors and/ or other field-actors over SIE-field structures and processes. These contestations can ‘unsettle’ the existing institutional environment (without necessarily changing it). This is complemented with an analysis of the relationships between these actors providing the preconditions for these contestations.

When it comes to relations between actors, for a long time, the field of Swiss energy cooperatives was highly fragmented and only weakly organised at the national level due to the strongly locally oriented individual energy cooperatives. Although there are considerable differences between the individual energy cooperatives in terms of some characteristics (size, degree of professionalisation, etc.), many of them are relatively similar when it comes to characteristics of the technology used (the very large majority use PV). Hence, despite their diversity regarding actor constellations, they are relatively homogeneous in terms of their activities and objectives (see Rivas et al. 2018). In the course of the consolidation of the field through the emergence of different intermediary actors in recent years, the local-only focus has been partially overcome. Nevertheless, the field still exhibits a high level of diversity, as these emerging actors emphasise and represent different aspects of energy cooperatives (renewable energy aspects, cooperative aspects, citizen participation aspects, new actors in the energy system).

When it comes to contestations in the field, major issues regard energy policymaking at federal level as well as the *raison d'être* and demarcation of energy cooperatives in general. Regarding influence on policymaking, the emerging intermediary actors, above all the “Association of Independent Energy Producers” VESE, have taken on advocacy functions at the federal political level. Subsequent to the introduction of the new Energy Act in 2018, there have been several new developments and readjustments at the level of ordinances (*Verordnungen*), and currently the energy act itself is being revised. All these amendments were subject to consultation procedures (*Vernehmlassungsprozesse*, see footnote 2, p. 26) in which VESE expressed its position. The main issues at stake here are the specific design of the subsidy schemes for renewable energies, bringing in the concerns of small producers such as energy cooperatives. So far, however, the cooperative character itself has not featured in this process. One other important point of contestation, which was also emphasised by other interviewed partners, is the current approach to the certificates of origin (HKN). The energy cooperatives have criticised that the Europe-wide accreditation leads to the price of these certificates being severely depressed by certificates issued by large foreign power plants (e.g., in Norway) thus exerting further stress on the viability of domestic PV plants and rendering economic business models less feasible. This practice has been described as the modern “indulgence trade”.

Other contestations, sometimes not fully explicit, concern the *raison d'être* and associated demarcation of the energy cooperatives field. Despite the leading role of VESE as the main intermediary, the demarcation, self-narrative and general direction of the Swiss energy cooperatives are not entirely obvious given the high diversity of other intermediaries; for instance, in the question of whether the focus should be on cooperative or citizen energy identity, whether it is more about promoting a solar technology, or whether it is more about empowering citizens and freeing them from dependencies on incumbent actors. This question is reinforced by new developments among incumbent actors in the Swiss energy system. This last phase since 2015 was also characterised by an increasing number of incumbent energy suppliers offering their own citizen participation schemes for PV facilities. These models provide a simple form of participation in which an effect is immediately visible on the consumer's/investor's own electricity bill (which is usually not the case when participating in energy cooperatives). Especially in urban areas, such participation models have often been highly successful and well visible. Since these models are limited to financial participation, the questions arise if these models are actual competitors to energy cooperatives (both economically and conceptually) as well as what exactly distinguishes them from cooperatives. Some interviewees welcomed these new models as they promote development of renewable energy:

"It is good that they [energy providers] understand that they have to do something. Up until 5 years ago, you could have thought that all energy providers would disappear as they did not seem to understand the need to adopt more modern business models. At least the big ones have done that now" (Interviewee 7).

However, it was also emphasised that these models are often more expensive for the participants than those of the cooperatives because the energy suppliers often are profit-oriented, because they cannot rely on voluntary work, and because the cooperative self-consumption models do not involve grid costs (Interviewee 4, Interviewee 7). Against this background, the success of the energy suppliers' participation models is surprising as the energy cooperatives could offer a similar constellation through sales of certificates of origin (HKN) to lower costs. An advantage of the participation models of energy suppliers might be that the effect of investment is directly visible on the electricity bill, which can usually only be provided by the energy suppliers and not by energy cooperatives.

Finally, another association of direct relevance to energy cooperatives was formed in 2018 with the "Association for citizen energy Switzerland" ASEC (Association suisse pour l'énergie citoyenne) in the French-speaking part of Switzerland. For a long time, there were only few energy cooperatives in this region. In 2015, the movie 'Demain' was a great success in cinemas, especially in the French-speaking areas, and led to more attention and even the founding of energy cooperatives (Interviewee 3). Inspired by energie partagée and négaWatt in France, ASEC was founded to improve the visibility and political representation of citizen energy initiatives.

«Isolation is one of the major challenges. The energy cooperatives worked separately even though they were maybe just be 20km apart. They did not even know the others existed. Public awareness and knowledge about these kinds of structures are the main challenges along with their political role. Now there is a political discussion on energy, but these actors have no voice because they do not exist in the political arena" (Interviewee 3).

Whereas the organisations mentioned so far have the reference point of decentralised renewable energy, further intermediary organisations have been founded in recent years which focus less on the energy-aspect but rather on the form of organisation. In 2018, "Cooperative Suisse" was created (among others by individuals associated with ADEV cooperative) with the aim to promote and support enterprises which credibly prioritise their social impact and not profit.

"There are already many such enterprises in Switzerland but so far there was no meta-aggregation which supports the cause with scientific data and gives the topic more publicity and visibility on a political level." (Interviewee 1).

Such enterprises include new energy cooperatives, especially as they do not primarily pursue the advancement of their members but broader social goals such as the implementation of the energy transition or questions of democratic citizen representation in the energy sector. Finally, in 2020, the *idée cooperative* was created, which sees itself as an association of cooperatives (understood as a legal form). In this association, too, the focus is not on energy but specifically on the cooperative subject. So far, the intermediary organisations focusing on energy aspects have been more central to the energy cooperatives than those focusing on the cooperative aspect. This is particularly evident when it comes to advocacy in federal energy policy processes.

Advocacy in federal policy-making process

The newly founded intermediary actors, above all VESE, began participating in the development of new legislation, especially by providing written statements in the consulting procedures (see footnote 2, p. 26), thus marking an important step in the establishment of the field. The concerns of the energy cooperatives (and similar actors) could be increasingly represented in federal-level policy processes. A first development of energy policy in which this was the case was the elaboration of a new energy law, which came into force in 2018 after a referendum in 2017 and anchored the Energy Strategy 2050 in law. Important changes for energy cooperatives in this new act were the regulation of self-consumption communities as well as the extension of the one-off investment grants scheme to larger plants and its establishment as the central instrument for the promotion of photovoltaic.

Especially the option for self-consumption communities allowed developments in the business model of energy cooperatives. Since the introduction of the new energy act (and in particular since subsequent ordinances as of 2019), it is possible for several consumers (e.g., in a multi-family house) to pool their consumption of electricity generated on site in self-consumption communities (see SONNET case study on “Local electricity exchange”). With this development at the regulatory level, new players appeared in the field which come close to the definition of energy cooperatives, namely existing housing cooperatives which become active in the energy sector by using photovoltaic installations and establishing self-consumption communities. One example of this is the “Rossfeld housing cooperative” in the city of Bern, which is partly self-supplying by means of three self-financed and operated PV systems on the roofs of the housing cooperatives’ buildings. Interestingly, it was advised by the “Energy Cooperative Switzerland” (*Energiegenossenschaft Schweiz*) which demonstrates the potential for cross-sectoral cooperation. However, such cooperation has rather been the exception so far, and housing cooperatives are currently at best marginally part of the field of energy cooperatives. Their main goal and activity remain the provision of affordable housing, they are organized in their own associations and there is currently little exchange and mutual perception with conventional energy cooperatives. On the other hand, the new model of self-consumption communities is highly relevant for the existing energy cooperatives. For many, however, this new model is both technically and organisationally demanding (see SONNET case study on the field “local electricity exchange in Switzerland” for further information about this self-consumption model), still reflecting the professionalisation challenge which many energy cooperatives in Switzerland face.

Finally, another recent development in the field is the foundation of energy cooperatives with a slightly different business activity. While energy cooperatives have typically been active in the financing and operation of PV systems in the past, recently, several cooperatives have been founded which particular focus on the installation of PV systems in a cooperative manner and thus improve the economic efficiency of the systems. Under the guidance of a professional, the members of these cooperatives participate as laypersons in the installation of the systems. In the previous energy cooperatives, this task was usually carried out by third parties.

Institutional work conducted by SIE-field actors and other field-actors

SONNET applies the concept of institutional work to acknowledge that actors can be knowledgeable agents who are able to influence and change institutions. Institutional work refers to the activities of SIE-field-actors and other field-actors that aim to create, maintain, and transform institutions. We are interested in why, how, when and where actors engaged in such institutional work to better understand the different forms of institutional work, types of work conducted (boundary work, strategy work, etc.), actors who are engaged (or not) in this work, and enabling and impeding factors to be able to conduct this work.

Institutional work of in the field of energy cooperatives mainly occurs in two ways, firstly, through serving as example and role model with their business activities thus attempting to change institutions on how to *do* and *organize* energy, i.e. through the cooperative members' engagement in the construction, financing and management of photovoltaic facilities or, secondly, through joint advocacy of representatives of cooperatives and of intermediary organizations in energy policy-making processes at the federal level, thus attempting to change formal institutions.

For many energy cooperatives, the expansion of solar power is the primary goal. The extent to which the institutional goal of serving as an example for the changing role of citizens is an explicit goal is not definitive. It might be the case that the latter was a central concern especially for energy cooperatives which emerged from the anti-nuclear movement, which therefore have a stronger political self-image, while in the case of newer energy cooperatives such an institutional change may still be an effect, but not a primarily intended goal. Similarly, the energy cooperatives in the 1990s had a strong pioneering spirit. One kind of institutional work was to try to shift the population's view of photovoltaic technology by showing on the ground that such systems work, or by pointing out their existence in the first place ('first photovoltaic system in the village').

Furthermore, through the emergence of intermediary organisations, networking and interest representation have recently become dominant forms of institutional work that SIE field actors are engaged in, thus concretely addressing institutional-regulatory conditions.

6 SUMMARY, SYNTHESIS AND CONCLUSIONS

6.1 How do SIEs and SIE-fields emerge, develop, and institutionalise over time?

In SONNET we think of social innovation in the energy sector (SIE) as combination of ideas, objects and/or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy. In the case of the Swiss energy cooperatives, the social innovation is first and foremost a fallback to existing, well-known solutions or *ways of doing* which have already proven their worth in other areas. After all, cooperative models have been used in Switzerland for centuries to tackle problems at a local level, bottom up and emerging within civil society. In the energy sector, too, cooperatives have already for a long time shown their suitability for supplying electricity to rural areas. However, in the course of the anti-nuclear protest movement from the 1970s onwards and the emerging climate and sustainability debate, new problem perceptions have emerged, for which the cooperative model has been employed as a solution. Against this backdrop, the socially innovative nature of new energy cooperatives lies in both the content and the form of these new problem perceptions and proposed solutions.

When it comes to the form, it must be emphasised, that among the almost 200 newly established energy cooperatives, not merely the use of the cooperative model in a new problem field is to be understood as a social innovation. Rather, it is also innovative that the cooperative model was applied in a problem area which is not characterised by individual economic needs but by broader societal and ecological challenges. With this perspective, it is thus less the cooperation in local activities which qualifies as social innovation, but rather the fact that such cooperation was not primarily applied to address local common good issues, but broader, even global challenges. This idea is well illustrated with the concept "think global, act local". When it comes to the specific content, aspects of social innovation appeared in the area of the goals and activities of energy cooperatives. From the point of view of the energy cooperatives, it was the confrontation with the incumbent energy system about the construction of new nuclear power plants which led to a problem perception of a democracy deficit i.e., lack of citizen control in essential questions of energy supply. This was to be counteracted by opportunities for direct participation in investment decisions via the cooperatives and by simultaneously promoting renewable energies. The central social innovation is therefore a shift of the concept of citizenship when it comes to energy policy, that is a change of social relations from voters and passive consumers to prosumers who actively co-shape developments in the energy system.

However, the strong emphasis on the social innovation of energy cooperatives as citizen participation has undergone a change in recent years. Particularly, the motives of the protest against nuclear power plants and of political participation seem to have somewhat eased in recent years. Rather pragmatically, the most important motive today is often simply the expansion of renewable energies in the form of PV or some case small scale hydro power plants. With this focus on quantifiable *hard* impact, especially in the course of the second wave of cooperative foundations, the importance of federal energy policy increased as it has a major impact on the economic viability of the business models of energy cooperatives (while this economic viability was perhaps not immediately central to the first wave with its symbolic goals). The development of the number of new start-ups since 2005 points to a highly formative role of federal support policies for the field of energy cooperatives. The long-term investment security guaranteed by the feed-in remuneration at cost scheme introduced in 2008 prompted a strong increase in the number of new foundations, which then dropped as soon as this subsidy was no longer available. This might be understood in a way that as the social innovation of cooperatives transformed (from the initial emphasis on citizen participation in the energy system to a primary function as a means of expanding PV), the institutional environment became more relevant as it is fundamental to this expansion purpose.

Finally, it is not only among energy cooperatives that a shift in social innovation is taking place as the idea of citizen participation diffused to the incumbent system. In recent years, several energy suppliers in cities have begun to set up their own participation models in which individual residents can participate financially in PV systems and experience a direct impact on their own electricity bills. In certain features, these models resemble the cooperative concept fairly closely. On the one hand, this can be interpreted in the sense that the social innovation which cooperatives are aspiring to is, at least in part, increasingly integrated into the established system. On the other hand, however, there is a risk that cooperative solutions may be seen as redundant if these models become even more widespread. The initial social innovation of energy cooperatives of a stronger participation of citizens in the energy system has thus become more widespread, yet in a modified form that does not necessarily do justice to the initial concern of such citizen participation, namely that of political co-determination.

6.2 How do SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the 'outside' institutional environment and thereby co-shape the SIE-field over time?

Various 'outside' institutional conditions shape the field of energy cooperatives. First of all, the application of the cooperative model itself is to be understood as a cultural institution. The idea of addressing common good issues at the local level, bottom-up and in self-responsibility through the form of cooperatives has a centuries-old tradition in Switzerland (for example in the management of alpine pastures). Cooperatives are also a frequently used model in the organisation of supply infrastructure or in the housing sector. Further 'outside' institutional conditions which shape the field are the federal state structure and the concomitant decentralised,

fragmented energy system with many small energy suppliers. Due to their great leeway in the federal system municipalities are in a position to substantially support energy cooperatives, which often turns them into local key players. Whilst often vital for the development of individual energy cooperatives, this strong presence of local structures is probably one of the reasons why energy cooperatives first only institutionalised at local level. Especially the first wave of energy cooperative foundations in the 1990s did not result in the formation of intermediary organisations and only in individual cases to professionalised and constantly developing cooperatives.

It was only after the second wave of foundations and with increasing recognition of the high relevance of the federal support policies for renewable energies that the mutual awareness and networking of individual cooperatives intensified. For a long time, energy cooperatives confined their focus mainly to their local environment, partly due to the federalist structure of the Swiss state and the small-scale energy system. Only in the last few years a number of new intermediary organisations have been founded that represent the interests of energy cooperatives in the genesis of federal energy policy and thus contributed to the networking and consolidation of the field at the national level. This may suggest that the evolvement of the SIE field towards a more interconnected and consolidated field ultimately hinged on an involvement of the SIE towards the expansion of PV as main purpose of energy cooperatives (as discussed in 6.1.).

6.3 What are the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work and change the 'outside' institutional environment?

Institutional work refers to the activities of SIE-field-actors and other field-actors that aim to create, maintain, and transform institutions. Institutional work and influencing change of 'outside' institutional environment by energy cooperatives mainly occurs in the two forms, firstly through serving as example and role model with their business activities thus attempting to change institutions on how to *do* and *organize* energy, i.e. through the cooperative members' engagement in the construction, financing and management of photovoltaic facilities or secondly, through joint advocacy of representatives of cooperatives and of intermediary organizations in energy policy-making processes at the federal level, thus attempting to change formal institutions.

In the first form, in terms of business activities, only a part of (the members of) energy cooperatives are directly involved in institutional work, in the sense that they deliberately seek to redefine the cultural institutions related to the role of citizens vis-a-vis the energy system—from consumers to prosumers—by setting an example of this themselves. Often their aim is simply to build more PV systems, and a resulting change in the role of citizens is at best a side effect. Hence, whether engagement in the business activities of the cooperatives can be considered institutional work depends on their goals and ambitions to actually serve as an example or role model for increased citizen participation, and not necessarily only on the activity itself.

It seems not entirely conclusive why some cooperatives have more far-reaching ambitions than others, or, in other words, what the factors are for some cooperatives and their members to engage in institutional work in the sense that they attempt to influence cultural institutions by means of serving as an example. An attempt to answer this question could be that older cooperatives, which mainly emerged as part of the anti-nuclear movement, have a stronger political self-image and thus also pursue such ambitions of a deliberate change in the conception of citizenship whereas newer ones are mainly concerned with a quantifiable and measurable increase in PV capacity. This might still imply changes in the role of citizenship. Without intentionality, however, it may not to be understood as institutional work but rather as a side effect.

If in fact the ambition to alter the concept of citizenship is a motive, factors for institutional work may be understood as factors for successful business activities since it is with such success that the energy cooperatives can act as role models and thus influence public perception and ultimately the institutions on how to organise the energy system. If so, key for success in these activities has been to find suitable roofs for PV facilities and corresponding sales opportunities for the generated electricity, which is enabled and impeded by several factors. Firstly, the introduction of cost-covering feed-in tariffs (KEV) at the federal level was a strong enabling factor for energy cooperatives' business activities and especially for their foundation in the first place. This policy instrument created a protected space with high investment security in which new energy cooperatives could be established. The discontinuation of the KEV option after 2012 and the resulting drop in the number of new foundations underlines the importance of such federal policy support. Secondly, after the discontinuation of the KEV option, support from municipalities or municipally owned energy suppliers was a central enabling factor. Support from these actors made it possible to guarantee investment security, e.g. through long-term contracts or by means of municipal policy instruments that were able to compensate for emerging gaps in the promotion of renewable energies. In the case of Switzerland, this strong role of the municipalities makes the federal system an indirect supporting factor for energy cooperatives (see Schmid et al. 2020). After all, it is only because of the extensive decision-making powers and financial resources that the municipalities are able to provide such support measures. Thirdly, energy suppliers with monopoly for the supply area in which the cooperatives are active can create both enabling and impeding conditions. On the one hand, they can buy the generated electricity from the energy cooperatives on terms that make possible a cost-covering operation of the solar plants. However, they are not necessarily legally obliged to do so. In other cases, where only the legal minimum is paid, this is to be seen as an impeding factor. In general, the strong dependence of the energy cooperatives on the pricing policy of the energy suppliers can certainly represent an impeding factor.

The second form of institutional work that representatives of cooperatives or intermediary organisations engage in is interest representation in the policy-making processes. The work then aims at changing the regulatory institutional environment. Only very few energy cooperatives are actively involved in this institutional work, especially when it comes to regulation at the federal level. More are likely to be active in influencing the institutional conditions at the local level, for example regarding municipal support policies for renewables or the pricing policy of energy suppliers. However, these institutional conditions tend to be part of the SIE-field

itself and not necessarily of the ‘outside’ institutional environment. The institutional work for adjustments of federal regulatory-institutional conditions is primarily conducted via interest groups, especially via the “Association of independent power producers” VESE. Yet, by far not all energy cooperatives are members of VESE, but they indirectly benefit from its work when shared concerns of energy cooperatives actually are taken into account in the federal policy-making process. One factor which may have fostered the formation of joint interest representation is the removal of the possibility for funding from the “Feed-in remuneration at cost” scheme (KEV) as this made the business environment more challenging but also strengthened the awareness that a common voice is important when it comes to future regulation.

7 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR OUR CITY PARTNERS, NATIONAL AND EU POLICY MAKERS AND SIE PRACTITIONERS

SONNET city partners

- If cities wish to support energy cooperatives, they may do this especially in two ways. Firstly, they can provide their own roofs and purchase the electricity generated by the cooperatives over a long-time horizon. Secondly, they can use ownership strategies or concession agreements towards the energy suppliers to encourage them to purchase the electricity generated by independent producers (such as energy cooperatives) in the area of supply on a long-term basis.

National and EU policy makers

- If there is a political objective to promote actors such as cooperatives, it is paramount not only to consider the economic efficiency when designing support instruments for renewable energies but also how easy it is to apply certain instruments. A major advantage of cost-covering feed-in tariff schemes has been their ease of use, which makes them well suited for small, non-professionalised actors. Other instruments, such as tendering procedures, in contrast, may risk being too complicated for such actors to benefit from as they often lack the necessary administrative capacity and knowledge as well as the option for diversification of risks.
- Fundamentally, it must be considered how, in the assessment of measures, the criterion of economic efficiency is to be weighed against other values and objectives which can only inadequately be translated into monetary or generally quantitative values, such as the acceptance of renewable energies or the democratic quality of decisions in the energy system.

SIE practitioners

- For individual cooperatives, it is worthwhile to continue the networking process already started and to think beyond the local level (even if the activities continue to be mainly local). One option might be to find inspiration in the housing cooperative sector, which has undergone a similar development in recent

- years.
- With respect to own consumption models especially, it might be worthwhile to seek increased cooperation with housing cooperatives. Although the cooperative form provides well suited structures for self-consumption communities in housing cooperatives, there is often a lack of expertise or even awareness of the existence of this model for self-consumption. In this context, energy cooperatives could function as service providers for housing cooperatives.
 - Finally, one suggestion is to sharpen the profile of energy cooperatives in communication. This could include the development of unique-selling points of energy cooperatives or the development of guidelines for municipalities on the advantages of working with energy cooperatives and how a possible cooperation should be structured through the different phases of the business process.

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9 ANNEX

Methodology

A total of ten interviews were completed for this case study. Some of them overlapped with the 'local electricity exchange' field. These interviews were then conducted in one conversation on both topics and took longer. The interviews were all done online via Zoom software. If the consent of the interview partners was given, the interviews were recorded and then summarized or partly transcribed. A complete transcription was omitted due to the available funds.

The interviews were supplemented with a document analysis, using mainly documents from the interviewed intermediary organisations (based on website search of these organisations) and existing research literature on energy cooperatives in Switzerland.

The case selection of the two SIE initiatives studied was based on two main factors. Firstly, both ADEV and Optima Solar cooperatives have had above-average success in building multiple PV systems, which makes them interesting cases in terms of success factors and innovative business models. Secondly, there were already established contacts to the two cases from previous research as well as through relationships of city partner Basel.

Documents reviewed

Link to which SIE-Initiative / field actor	Author name	Document name	Document type	Year	Link to reference
Primary sources					
ADEV	ADEV	25 Jahre engagiert für die Energiewende - Jubiläums-broschüre 1985-2010	Anniversary brochure	2010	https://www.adev.ch/assets/uploads/files/broschueren/Jubilaeumsbroschuere-25-Jahre.pdf
Albert Koechling Foundation (AKS)	AKS	Erfolgreiche Unterstützung von Energiegenossenschaften	Press release	2019	http://www.aks-stiftung.ch/05_medienmitteilungen/medienmitteilungen2019

					/2019-medienmitteilung-energiegenossenschaften.pdf
Albert Koechling Foundation (AKS)	AKS	Leitfaden Musterablauf Gründung Energiegenossenschaften	Guideline, Template	n.d.	http://www.aks-stiftung.ch/02_projekte/05-umwelt/energiegenossenschaften/leitfaden---musterablauf-gruendung-energiegenossenschaft.pdf
Optima Solar	Optima Solar	Wie weiter mit der lokalen, dezentralen Stromproduktion?	Letter to federal council	2020	https://www.optimasolar-solothurn.ch/2020/04/14/wie-weiter-mit-der-lokalen-dezentralen-stromproduktion/
Optima Solar	Optima Solar	Über uns	Website	2020	https://www.optimasolar-schweiz.ch/%C3%BCber-uns-1/
VESE		Gesetzliche Grundlagen zur Einspeisung	Website		https://www.vese.ch/gesetzliche-grundlagen/
VESE	Sachs, Walter	Ziele VESE	Presentation		https://www.vese.ch/wp-content/uploads/VESE_Ziele.pdf
VESE	Lüthi, Heini	Stellungnahme zur Umsetzung des ersten Massnahmenpaketes zur Energiestrategie 2050: Änderungen auf Verordnungsstufe	Opinion in consultative process (Vernehmlassungsverfahren)	2017	https://www.vese.ch/wp-content/uploads/StellungnahmeES2050Verordnungen_V05_20170504.pdf
VESE		Unrechtmässig Gebühren verlangt	Press release		https://www.vese.ch/wp-content/uploads/2020.02.26_MM_Unrechtm%C3%A4ssig-Geb%C3%BChren-verlangt.pdf
Secondary sources					
Swiss energy cooperatives in general	Rivas, Juliana; Schmid, Benjamin; Seidl, Irmi	Energiegenossenschaften in der Schweiz: Ergebnisse einer Befragung	Report	2018	https://www.wsl.ch/de/publikationen/energiegenossenschaften-in-der-schweiz-ergebnisse-einer-befragung.html
Swiss energy cooperatives in general	Meister, Thomas; Schmid,	How municipalities support energy cooperatives: survey	Journal article	2020	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s13705-020-00248-3

	Benjamin; Seidl, Irmi; Klagge, Britta	results from Germany and Switzerland.			
Swiss energy cooperatives in general	Schmid, Benjamin; Seidl, Irmi	Zivilgesellschaftliches Engagement und Rahmenbedingungen für erneuerbare Energie in der Schweiz.	Book chapter	2018	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-658-09416-4_64
Swiss energy cooperatives in general	Schmid, Benjamin; Meister, Thomas; Klagge, Britta; Seidl, Irmi	Energy Cooperatives and Municipalities in Local Energy Governance Arrangements in Switzerland and Germany	Journal article	2020	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1070496519886013?journalCode=jeda
Swiss energy cooperatives in general	Ebers Broughel, Anna; Stauch, Alexander; Schmid, Benjamin; Vuichard, Pascal	Consumer (Co-) Ownership in Renewables in Switzerland	Book chapter	2019	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-93518-8_20

List of interviewees

Code	Name of initiative / organisation	Type of organisation	Duration hh:mm	Date (dd.mm.yyyy)
Interviewee 1	Association CooperativeSuisse	Other field actor	01:00	20.06.20
Interviewee 2	Albert-Koechlin Foundation	SIE field actor	01:20	25.06.20
Interviewee 3	Association suisse pour l'énergie citoyenne ASEC	SIE field actor	00:50	08.07.20
Interviewee 4	Optima Solar Genossenschaft Schweiz	SIE-initiative	01:30	13.07.20
Interviewee 5	Association Idée coopérative	Other field actor	00:55	21.07.20
Interviewee 6	Housing cooperative Rossfeld Bern	SIE-initiative	01:30	22.07.20

Interviewee 7	Association of Independent Energy Producers VESE & Energiewendegenossenschaft Basel	SIE field actor, SIE-initiative	02:00	23.07.20
Interviewee 8	ADEV cooperative	SIE-initiative	01:20	28.07.20
Interviewee 9	Association of Swiss Electricity Companies VSE	Other field actor	01:15	29.07.20

Participatory Observations: List of meetings and events attended

Code	Title	Type	Date (dd.mm.yyyy)	Duration (hh:mm)
Participatory observation 1	Neue Modelle für Solargenossenschaften	Webinar organized by VESE on case of association 'sunraising'	20.05.2020	01:00

Timeline and actor network of COOPERATIVE ORGANISATIONAL MODELS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY IN SWITZERLAND

DATE/ TIME	TYPE OF EVENT	DESCRIPTION OF EVENT	QUOTE & SOURCE e.g. document, interviewee
Historical background: 1895-1925		Many cooperatives are founded to build distribution grids and provide electricity especially to rural areas (around 150 of which are still in operation today)	Schmid and Seidl, 2018
PHASE 1: First wave of new foundations: Anti-nuclear protest and pioneering renewables (1985-2000)			
1970-1988	External shock and trend	Anti-nuclear protests, especially against nuclear power plant 'Kaiseraugst'	Interview VESE
1974	SIE-field event	Formation of Swiss Association for Solar Energy SSES	Interview VESE
1976	SIE-field event	Formation of Swiss Energy Foundation SES	Interview VESE

1985	SIE-initiative event	Formation of 'Working Group Decentralised Energy Supply (Arbeitsgemeinschaft Dezentrale Energieversorgung) ADEV (first energy cooperative focusing on renewables)	Interview ADEV,
1986	External shock and trend	Chernobyl nuclear accident	Interview VESE
1990	Policy 'event'	Constitutional anchoring of energy policy as task of the federal government after referendum & 'Energienutzungsbeschluss' including '16-Räppler'	Rieder and Stotz 2018; Sager, 2014; Interviewee 8,
1985-1998	SIE-field event	First wave of energy cooperative foundations with focus on renewables (around 40 cooperatives)	Schmid and Seidl 2018
PHASE 2: Intermezzo and developments in Swiss energy policy (1998-2005)			
1998	Policy 'event'	First federal energy law	Rieder and Stotz 2018; Sager, 2014
2002	Policy 'event'	Liberalization of the electricity market is rejected in referendum	Sager, 2014
PHASE 3: Second wave of new foundations and federal RE support schemes (2005-2012)			
2005	Policy 'event'	Introduction of federal scheme to support renewables: 'Financing of additional costs' scheme (Mehrkostenfinanzierung)	Weibel, 2011; Rieder and Stotz 2018
2006		Formation of Swissolar (Association of PV service providers and industry)	Interview VESE
2007	Policy 'event'	Electricity supply act (partial liberalization of electricity market: only for large consumers) & Energy Perspectives 2035 as basis for federal energy strategy	Rieder and Stotz 2018
2007	SIE-field event	Number of newly founded energy cooperatives per year starts to increase	Schmid and Seidl, 2018

2009	Policy 'event'	Introduction of federal feed-in tariff 'Feed-in remuneration at cost' (Kostendeckende Einspeisevergütung) KEV	Rieder and Stotz 2018
2011	External shock and trend	Fukushima nuclear accident	
2011	Policy 'event'	Federal government starts developing 'Energy Strategy 2050' (Energiestrategie 2050) including decision to phase-out nuclear power	Rieder and Stotz 2018
2012	SIE-field event	Number of newly founded energy cooperatives per year peaks	Schmid and Seidl, 2018
PHASE 4: Aggravating conditions: Weakening of federal support for renewable energies, uncertainty and decline of number of new foundations (2012-2014)			
2012	Policy 'event' /	Due to the limited financial resources available for the feed-in tariff KEV, there is hardly any prospect of KEV subsidies for new plants (waiting list too long)	
2013	SIE-field event	Formation of cooperative federation 'Optima Solar Switzerland'	Interview Optima Solar Schweiz
2014	Policy 'event'	Introduction of 'One-off investment grants' (Einmalvergütung) as alternative to KEV support & legal recognition and regulation of the right to self-consume of self-produced energy on site	Rieder and Stotz 2018
PHASE 5: Kick-off of self-structuring of the field through emergence of intermediary organisations (2015-heute)			
2015	SIE-field event	Formation of 'Association of independent power producers' (Verband unabhängiger Energieversorger) VESE as sub-group of SSES	Interview VESE
2015	External shock and trend	Movie 'Tomorrow' in cinemas inspired people to become more active in energy transition especially in French-speaking part of Switzerland	Interview ASEC

2015	SIE-field event	First semi-annual meeting of the VESE	
2016	SIE-field event	Start of program of Albert-Koechlin Association to support energy cooperatives in Central Switzerland	Interview Albert Koechlin Stiftung
2016	SIE-initiative event	Foundation of 'Energy Transition Cooperative Basel (Energiewende Genossenschaft Basel)	Interview VESE
2017	Policy 'event'	First package of measures of Energy Strategy 2050 (including new Energy Act) is accepted in referendum	
2018	Policy 'event'	New Energy Act is in force, including new regulation of self-consumption communities (Zusammenschluss zum Eigenverbrauch) ZEV	
2018	SIE-field event	Formation of CooperativeSuisse	Interview CooperativeSuisse
2018	SIE-field event	Formation of Association for citizen energy Switzerland (Association suisse pour l'énergie citoyenne) ASEC	Interview ASEC
2018	SIE-field event	Stabilization of the annual number of newly founded energy cooperatives (preliminary end of downward trend)	Schmid, Seidl, 2018; Rost, 2020
2018-2020	External shock and trend / SIE-field event	Repeated consultations on and adaptation of the energy regulation	
2020	SIE-field event	Formation of association 'idée coopérative'	Interview idée coopérative
2020	External shock and trend / SIE-field event	Consultation procedure for revision of the Energy Act	

Actor network

Actor name	Type of actor	SHORT DESCRIPTION OF MAIN ROLE, AIM, EXAMPLE OF MAIN ACTIVITY	SHORT DESCRIPTION OF RELATIONS TO OTHER ACTORS (characteristics)
ADEV	SIE-initiative	<p>Oldest “new” energy cooperative</p> <p>Aims at producing energy as decentrally as possible where it is used for lighting, household electricity, heat and electromobility.</p> <p>Builds and operates solar power plants, small hydroelectric power plants, wind energy plants as well as central heating plants and local heating grids..</p>	Knowledge exchange
Optima Solar Schweiz	SIE-initiative	<p>Cooperative federation of three Optima Solar cooperatives.</p> <p>Aims at facilitating the energy transition for everyone throughout Switzerland according to a uniform and successful model and at increasing the proportion of PV electricity in the grid.</p>	Providing advice, providing administrative services
VSE	Field actor	<p>Sector association of Swiss electricity companies</p> <p>Platform for representation of interests of the Swiss electricity sector. Engagement for reliable national and international framework conditions, a positive image of electricity and a secure, marketable, competitive, sustainable and innovative electricity supply.</p>	Networking, lobbying, knowledge exchange for energy suppliers, only limited relation to energy cooperatives (except “old” grid-operating cooperatives)
CooperativeSuisse (new SENS)	Field actor - enable	<p>Platform for social entrepreneurship Switzerland</p> <p>Aims at promoting enterprises that credibly place their social impact and not primarily profit in the centre; supporting the issue with scientific data and giving the topic more publicity and visibility on a political level. Main activities: Creating publicity; Network; Start-up & Innovation</p>	Networking, introducing element of social entrepreneurship

idée coopérative	Field actor - enable	Competence centre for cooperative model Providing data and knowledge on cooperative model; networking of fragmented cooperatives, political interest representation for cooperative model	Networking, Knowledge
ASEC	SIE-field actor - intermediary	Association functioning as network organisation in the field of citizen energy in Switzerland Represent all the initiatives that define themselves or that we classify under citizen energy; organized first energy citizen day in French-speaking Switzerland in 2018	Networking, political advocacy, increase visibility of initiatives
Albert-Koechlin Stiftung (energy cooperatives programme=	SIE-field actor - intermediary	Programme of foundation 'Albert-Koechlin' to support foundation of many locally anchored energy cooperatives in Central Switzerland that function as seed for local energy transition developments. Conceptional support in the foundation phase; financial contribution to the first plant; consulting by a specialist; exchange of knowledge	Financial support and know-how support; Knowledge-exchange, networking,
SSES	Field actor - enable	Swiss Association for Solar Energy, organisation for the interests of producers and consumers of solar power Aiming at promotion of the use of renewable energies, especially solar energy. Publication of the specialist journal "Erneuerbare Energien"; info evenings on the subject of "Does my system work properly" System checks for solar system; forumE- an energy transition online forum for questions about renewable energies; information and advice	Umbrella organisation of the VESE, pioneer in call for energy transition
Swissolar	Field actor - enable	Swiss Solar Energy Association represents the Swiss solar industry, i.e. all companies and institutions of the solar industry as well as organisations that support the concerns of the solar industry. Spokesperson for political sector interests and service organisation in the fields of joint advertising, information, education and quality assurance.	No direct relation, political engagement and services for solar technology

SES	Field actor - enable	<p>Foundation for a smart, environmentally, and humane energy policy.</p> <p>Aims at efficient use of energy and the promotion and use of renewable energy sources. Showing ways to detach Switzerland from the disastrous dependence on a fossil-nuclear energy supply.</p> <p>Political engagement (but act independently and in a politically neutral manner and exclusively common good oriented). Contact and exchange with authorities, politics, economy, science, media and citizens.</p>	No direct relation, political engagement for renewable energies and energy efficiency, organisation of events
VESE	SIE-field actor - intermediary	<p>Association for independent power producers</p> <p>Aims at public and political advocacy for decentralised, independent energy production, networking and support of members</p> <p>Consulting, elaboration of studies and manuals, organisation of expert events, statements in consultation procedures</p>	Networking (bi-annual conferences), knowledge exchange, providing advice, joint activities, lobbying